

Acetylacetonato Complexes of (η -Cyclopentadienyl, η -Methyl Cyclopentadienyl) Titanium(IV)

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A series of the compounds of the type $(ABTiL)^+X^-$ (where $A=\eta-C_5H_5$, $B=\eta-CH_2C_5H_4$, L =conjugate base of acetylacetonate and $X^-=ClO_4^-, BF_4^-, ZnCl_2(H_2O)^-, SnCl_2^-, CdCl_2^-, HgCl_2^-, FeCl_4^-, Br^-$ or I^-) have been prepared and characterised. The ligand L appears to be chelating and the titanium atom is essentially tetracoordinate. The bonding in these complexes is discussed.

SIX coordinate complexes of the type ML_2X_2 (where $L=\beta$ -diketone and $X=\sigma$ bonded carbanions), which were synthesized, include (L =acetylacetonate), $M=Sn$ and $X=Me^{1-3}$ or Ph^{1-4} as well as $M=Pb$, $X=Me^5$ or Ph^6 . Complexes having *trans*-configuration are thermodynamically favoured¹⁻³, whereas complexes with *cis* configuration are energetically more favourable with X ligands other than carbanions as, for example in $Sn(acac)_2Cl_2$.^{5,7} Complexes of the type $(A_2ML)^+X^-$ where L is the conjugate base of acetylacetonate, dibenzoylmethane, benzoylacetone and tropolone, X^- is $BF_4^-, ClO_4^-, PF_6^-, ASF_6^-, Fe_3CSO_3^-, Cl_3CSO_3^-, Ph_3B^-, I^-, NCS^-, NCSe^-, FeCl_4^-, CoCl_2^-, ZnCl_2(H_2O)^-, SnCl_2^-, CdCl_2^-$ and $SnCl_2^+$ and M is $Ti(IV)$, $V(IV)$ ⁸⁻⁹ have been reported. In all these complexes L appeared to be chelating and the metal was essentially four coordinate.

This paper deals with the preparation and characterization of complexes of the type $(ABTiL)^+X^-$ where L is the conjugate base of acetylacetonate and $X^-=ClO_4^-, BF_4^-, I^-, Br^-, FeCl_4^-, ZnCl_2^-, SnCl_2^-, CdCl_2^-$ and $HgCl_2^+$. Only one coordinating mode for one bidentate ligand to $ABTi(IV)$ moiety is observed and titanium(IV) is four coordinate in these complexes.

Experimental

Reagents and Techniques :

For conductivity measurements $PhNO_2$ was purified as described by Fay and Lowry¹⁰. $ABTiCl_2$ was prepared¹¹ by refluxing $ATiCl_3$ with $BTi(I)$ in THF.

Preparation of the Complexes :

A mixture of $ABTiCl_2$ and excess of acetylacetonate in H_2O was stirred for 2 hr and filtered. To the clear filtrate was added a concentrated aqueous

solution of $NaClO_4$ or $NaBF_4$ dropwise until no more precipitate formed. The precipitate was collected and washed several times with $EtOH$ and Et_2O . Recrystallization from $MeOH$ gave ~70% yield of perchlorate or fluoroborate complex.

A solution of $(ABTiL)^+Cl^-$ was prepared by stirring for 1 hr a suspension of $ABTiCl_2$ and acetylacetonate in H_2O . To this solution was added a concentrated aqueous solution of KI or KBr . The precipitates formed were collected, dried and recrystallized from CH_2Cl_2 to give ~70% yield of iodide or bromide complex. An aqueous solution of $(ABTiL)^+Cl^-$ was prepared as described above. To this solution was added concentrated aqueous solutions of $FeCl_3$, $ZnCl_2$, $SnCl_2$, $CdCl_2$ or $HgCl_2$ respectively. Addition of $NaCl$ aids the precipitation. Each complex precipitate was collected, washed and dried to give ~90% yield.

Physical Measurements :

The IR spectra in the region 4000-250 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model-621 grating spectrophotometer in KBr . $^1Hn.m.r.$ spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 n.m.r. spectrometer at a sweep width of 500 H_z using TMS as an internal standard. Conductance measurements were made in $PhNO_2$ using Beckman RC-18A conductivity bridge. Molecular weight of the complexes were determined ebullioscopically.

Results and Discussion

$ABTiCl_2$ on refluxing in water gives cationic species, out of which $[ABTi(OH)]^+$ predominates^{12,13}. The complexes reported herein have been prepared by the reaction, represented for perchlorate complex :

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA FOR (ABTiL) $^+X^-$

Complex	Conductance $\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mole^{-1}	Concentration mM	Molecular wt. Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.) %				Colour and m.p.
				C	H	halogen	Ti	
(ABTiL)ClO ₄	28.8	1.20	393 (990)	48.98 (49.17)	4.76 (4.86)	9.23 (9.10)	12.64 (12.29)	Brownish violet stable upto 350°C
(ABTiL)BF ₄	31.9	1.30	380 (377)	50.60 (50.82)	5.14 (5.02)	20.60 (20.11)	13.00 (12.70)	Violet 205°C d
(ABTiL)I	30.5	1.30	418 (477)	46.82 (45.94)	4.68 (4.54)	30.64 (30.39)	11.80 (11.49)	Yellow brown 160°C d
(ABTiL)Br	29.5	1.25	369 (370)	52.82 (51.76)	5.08 (5.12)	22.02 (21.88)	12.50 (12.93)	Black 110°C
(ABTiL) ₂ CdCl ₄	55.8	0.30	840 (836)	47.02 (45.91)	4.70 (4.54)	17.64 (16.97)	11.87 (11.47)	Black 157°C d
(ABTiL)HgCl ₄	26.6	0.25	602 (598)	51.91 (52.06)	3.21 (3.17)	18.00 (17.78)	8.54 (8.03)	Dark Brown 110°C
(ABTiL)ZnCl ₂ .H ₂ O	23.4	1.55	479 (480)	40.21 (39.92)	4.12 (3.95)	21.88 (22.15)	10.50 (9.98)	Dark Brown 143°C
(ABTiL)SnCl ₄	28.5	0.50	518 (516)	35.99 (37.19)	3.80 (3.68)	22.00 (20.68)	—	Chocolate Buff 198°C d
(ABTiL)FeCl ₄	28.6	0.30	494 (489)	40.28 (39.26)	4.00 (3.88)	30.02 (29.03)	10.05 (9.81)	Dark red 200°C d

 TABLE 2—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFT (VALUES IN Hz) FOR (ABTiL) $^+X^-$

Complex	C ₅ H ₅ ring protons	CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ ring protons	-CH ₃ protons of acetylacetonate	-CH ₃ protons of CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ ring	→OH protons of acetylacetonate	Solvent
(ABTiL)ClO ₄	-423	-438 t	-408 t	-171	-141	-398 (OD ₂) ₂ CO
(ABTiL)BF ₄	-423	-441 t	-405 t	-144	-126	-398 (OD ₂) ₂ CO
(ABTiL)I	-404	-422 t	-388 t	-188	-118	-370 ODCl ₄
(ABTiL)Br	-401	-418 t	-381 t	-133	-116	-367 ODCl ₄
(ABTiL) ₂ CdCl ₄	-411	-428 t	-399 t	-135	-114	-384 D ₂ O
(ABTiL)ZnCl ₂ .H ₂ O	-426	-438 t	-411 t	-144	-128	-393 (OD ₂) ₂ CO
(ABTiL)HgCl ₄	-426	-438 t	-414 t	-144	-126	-396 (OD ₂) ₂ CO
(ABTiL)SnCl ₄	-423	-435 t	-411 t	-133	-123	-368 (OD ₂) ₂ CO

t=triplet.

* Additional band (-228Hz) is exhibited due to coordinated H₂O molecule.

Even on employing high concentration of acetylacetonate, no *bis*(acetylacetonato) chelate could be isolated as the actual free ligand concentration in the solution remains low due to decomposition of ABTi(IV) with the breaking of Ti-ring bonds above pH 2.8.

The molecular weight determination in benzene indicate that these complexes are monomeric. Conductivity measurements in PhNO₂ (molar conductance in between 31.9-23.4 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$) indicated these complexes to be 1:1 electrolyte except (ABTiL)₂CdCl₄ which is 1:2 electrolyte (molar conductance 55.8 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$). Physical data for these complexes are given in Table 1.

¹Hn.m.r. Spectra :

¹Hn.m.r. spectra of these complexes exhibit five

distinct resonances (i) a sharp signal due to C₅H₅ ring protons, (ii) two unsymmetrical triplets due to CH₃C₅H₄ ring protons, (iii) a sharp signal due to γ proton of acetylacetonate, (iv) a sharp signal due to methyl protons of acetylacetonate and (v) a sharp signal due to -CH₃ protons of CH₃C₅H₄ ring. The integrals of these resonances are in the ratio of 5:4:1:6:3. ¹Hn.m.r. data are given in Table 2.

Infrared Spectra :

The possibility of bonding of acetylacetonate ion by simple hard sphere coulombic interactions to (ABTi)²⁺ is ruled out on the basis that in such a case a *bis* complex, in contrast to the observations in the present investigation with four oxygen atoms in XY plane and parallel cyclopentadienyl, methylcyclopentadienyl rings ($w=180^\circ$) could be isolated. Such a structure would minimise the coordination

number for the metal atom and simultaneously maximise the total overlap of rings.

Bradley and Holloway¹⁴ have reported the vibrational frequencies for the coordinated acetylacetonate ligand in TiL_2Cl_2 as $\nu C=O$, 1550 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C=C$, 1520 cm^{-1} ; and $\nu Ti-O$, 472 cm^{-1} . The values assigned here for (ABTiL) ClO_4 and (ABTiL) BF_4 respectively are $\nu C=O$ (1540, 1538 cm^{-1}); $\nu C=C$, (1515 cm^{-1} , 1510 cm^{-1}); and $\nu Ti-O$, (465, 463 cm^{-1}), which are very similar.

π -Bonded cyclopentadienyl and methylcyclopentadienyl rings are identified in the ir spectra of these complexes by the appearance of ir active bands which are in accordance with the assignment made by Fritz¹⁵. In addition to the bands metal-halogen stretching bands of complex chloro anions also appear at $\sim$ (240-390) cm^{-1} .

TABLE 3—IR ACTIVE BANDS AND THEIR ASSIGNMENT FOR (ABTiL)X

(ABTiL) ClO_4 cm^{-1}	(ABTiL) BF_4 cm^{-1}	Assignment
3090m	3100m	$\nu C-H$ (rings)
2905w	2905w	$\nu C-H$ (CH_3 of $CH_2C_5H_4$)
1540vs,	1538vs,	
1352m, 1284m	1352m, 1284m	$\nu C=O$ (acetylacetonate)
1515vs	1510vs	$\nu C=O$ (acetylacetonate)
1497sh, 1327s	1440sh, 1325s	C-C ring stretching
1428s	1427s	CH_3 deg. def. (acetylacetonate)
1188w	1185w	acetylacetonate in plane bend.
1130m	1125m	symmetric ring breathing
1092vs,br	—	$\nu_s(ClO_4^-)$
1025m	1025m	C-H asymmetric in plane deformation rings
860s, 820s	865s, 825s	C-H out of plane bending rings
792m	792m	out of plane bending (acetylacetonate)
635m	—	$\nu_s(ClO_4^-)$
465s	463s	TiO_2 stretching
427s	425s	Ti ring stretch

v=very; s=strong; m=medium; w=weak; sh=shoulder; br=broad.

Table 3 lists the ir active bands and their assignment for (ABTiL) X ($X=ClO_4, BF_4$). The ir spectra of other complexes are similar.

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